

Calibration of fuel performance models using OFFBEAT solver: addressing aleatoric uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

Bayesian calibration offers a robust framework for improving the predictive performance of nuclear fuel performance models, including for quantities such as fuel centerline temperature (FCT). Traditional techniques often struggle to fully capture aleatoric variability in model parameters and may underestimate the uncertainty of the model predictions. This study shows the usage of a hierarchical Bayesian calibration framework based on Metropolis-Hastings (MH) within Gibbs algorithm to address aleatoric uncertainty in model parameters. The methodology integrates a sensitivity analysis to identify the most influential model parameters, Gaussian Process surrogates of the OFFBEAT solver to reduce computational cost, and Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithm for parameter inference. Calibration results demonstrate that, for the inference of the most sensitive parameter, UO_2 thermal conductivity, the hierarchical approach successfully recovers the target distribution and generates a predictive posterior that encompasses experimental data not included in the calibration process, within the 95% uncertainty bounds. When extended to the five most influential parameters, the method yields slightly broader posterior distributions and less stable convergence due to parameter interactions. Nevertheless, the predictive quantiles indicate statistical consistency between model predictions and experimental measurements, demonstrating that the calibration successfully reproduces the experimental data within the stated uncertainty bounds. This study highlights the robustness of hierarchical calibration for sensitive parameters and its capability to provide realistic uncertainty estimates in the case of aleatoric uncertainty in model parameters. Future work will extend the framework to account for model bias and the time-dependency of quantities of interest.

Keywords: Hierarchical Calibration, Markov Chain Monte Carlo, Aleatoric Uncertainty, Sensitivity Analysis, Gaussian Processes

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional Bayesian calibration techniques, widely used in nuclear modeling, often struggle to accurately quantify the full spectrum of uncertainty in predictive simulations [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. In previous work [5], it was demonstrated that the standard approach of combining Gaussian Process (GP) surrogates with Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling systematically under-performs in parameter inference and underestimates output uncertainty when applied to models affected by bias and aleatoric uncertainty. This limitation stems from the inability of these classical Bayesian formulations to consider systematic model error (bias) and random model parameters uncertainty, resulting in biased and overconfident posterior predictions.

The present study extends that analysis by using a hierarchical calibration framework explicitly designed to account for both sources of uncertainty. The proposed approach, also known as uncertainty inflation mechanism, is based on the Metropolis-Hasting within Gibbs algorithm [4]. This enhancement ensures a more realistic propagation of uncertainty and mitigates the underestimation of predictive posterior variance observed in traditional methods.

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The methodology is implemented and tested using the OFFBEAT fuel performance solver [6] to calibrate the fuel centerline temperature (FCT) at End-of-Life (EOL). As in previous study, the set of rods under analysis is derived from Turkey Point Nuclear Generating Unit 3 [7] and an artificial dataset with known ground truth is constructed to qualitatively and quantitatively assess the method's ability to recover model parameters and uncertainty bounds. This study will focus on the calibration performance in addressing aleatoric uncertainty on the model parameters to infer The source of uncertainty arising from model bias is not the primary focus here and will be considered in future work.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the construction of the synthetic dataset and the OFFBEAT simulation setup. Section 3 presents the application of the calibration framework and discusses the results, including a comparison between the hierarchical and the standard Bayesian approach. Finally, Section 4 concludes the study and outlines directions for future work.

2. APPLICATION CASE STUDY

This study focuses on the calibration of fuel performance models representative of existing PWR fuel rods from the Turkey Point Unit 3 (TP3) reactor, using the OFFBEAT solver. The quantity of interest (QoI) is the *fuel centerline temperature* (FCT), a key parameter in evaluating fuel behavior under both normal operating and accidental conditions. To rigorously assess the effectiveness of the calibration framework, it is opted not to use experimental benchmark data (e.g., from IFPE [8]) but instead to generate artificial datasets. This approach allows full control over the reference (*true*) model and enables the explicit introduction of any number of experiments with specific variability. By doing so, it is possible to evaluate the capability of the hierarchical calibration approach to recover the true values of the model parameters and accurately represent uncertainty in the posterior predictions. The following section describes the OFFBEAT model setup and the procedures used to generate the aleatoric uncertainty in the synthetic data.

2.1. TP3 rods OFFBEAT modeling

Starting from the findings of previous work [5], the calibration exercise is focused on a selected subset of eight fuel rods (1, 10, 20, 31, 44, 58, 67, 99), followed by validation on an additional set of eight rods. For a detailed description of the rod data source and the retrieval procedure, the reader is referred to Reference [5].

Each model is characterized by a set of input and model parameters, defined within the model input files, which include geometric and material properties as well as power histories. The focus of this study is on a subset of 17 model parameters implemented in the OFFBEAT framework, representing material property correlations and behavioral models. These parameters include density, specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity, emissivity, elastic modulus, Poisson's ratio, and thermal expansion coefficient for both fuel (UO₂) and cladding (modeled as ZIRLO, Zirconium Low Oxidation alloy) along with models accounting for densification, swelling, and relocation effects, as shown in Table I.

2.2. Synthetic experimental datasets: generation of aleatoric input uncertainty

The synthetic dataset represents a key element of this analysis, as it enables a controlled evaluation of the source of uncertainty that is subsequently addressed in the calibration exercise. To account for aleatoric uncertainty, the model parameters targeted for inference are varied across the different rods. Experiment-specific values are generated by sampling from realistic probability distributions, as defined in reference [9]. These distributions are modeled as truncated Gaussians, with lower and upper bounds at the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles respectively. The varied model parameters are listed in Table I, where the reported uncertainty ranges correspond to these $\pm 1.96\sigma$ intervals (i.e., covering approximately 95% of the probability mass) for each distribution. This ensures that the sampled values remain

within a physically realistic and statistically representative range, promoting robustness in downstream modeling and calibration. Finally, for each rod, a forward model is computed to estimate the FCT and a Gaussian noise is introduced to account for the measurement uncertainty. By following this approach, eight experimental rods are generated, each associated with specific values of the model parameters targeted for inference. These values are treated as the reference (or “true”) targets in the calibration results analysis and can be viewed as samples from the underlying target distribution that would be represented by a larger ensemble of rods affected by aleatoric uncertainties. In the following analysis, both the eight target values and their corresponding underlying distributions are shown in the visualization plots (Figures 2 and 4) to clearly illustrate the true reference used for calibration.

Table I. The selected 17 model parameters and associated $\pm 1.96\sigma$ value ranges (95% interval) used for the experimental data set.

Category	Parameter	Value Range (%)
Fuel	Density ρ	± 2
	Heat capacity C_p	± 5
	Thermal conductivity k	± 10
	Emissivity ε	± 5
	Young’s modulus E	± 5
	Poisson’s ratio ν	± 5
	Thermal expansion α_T	± 15
Cladding	Density ρ	± 2
	Heat capacity C_p	± 5
	Thermal conductivity k	± 10
	Emissivity ε	± 5
	Young’s modulus E	± 5
	Poisson’s ratio ν	± 5
	Thermal expansion α_T	± 15
Behaviour	Densification	± 10
	Relocation	± 10
	Swelling	± 20

3. CALIBRATION FRAMEWORK

To achieve an efficient and computationally feasible calibration, this research introduces a specific framework that integrates several complementary techniques. The methodology begins with a sensitivity analysis to identify the most influential model parameters, thereby reducing the dimensionality of the calibration problem. To further manage computational demands, surrogate modeling techniques are employed to emulate the computationally expensive model simulations. Finally, a hierarchical calibration approach is applied to account for aleatoric variability among the experiments. In this section, each of these techniques is described in detail and its application to the selected case study is demonstrated.

3.1. Sensitivity analysis: Morris’ method application

The initial stage of the proposed framework involves performing a preliminary sensitivity analysis prior to the calibration exercise. This analysis is performed for each fuel rod model to identify the model parameters with the greatest influence on the FCT. It is conducted using the Dakota software suite, specifically its implementation of the Morris One-At-A-Time (MOAT) method via the PSUADE (Problem Solving Environment for Uncertainty Analysis and Design Exploration) interface [10]. The theoretical background of the method is discussed in detail in Reference [11].

Figure 1c presents a summary of the sensitivity analysis results. To provide a comprehensive overview, rather than displaying the absolute mean and standard deviation for each fuel rod individually, the distribution of these metrics across the rods using the 95% quantile intervals is depicted. This approach highlights the overall variability and importance of each input parameter. The analysis identifies the key parameters with the greatest influence on FCT. Accordingly, fuel thermal conductivity, density, thermal expansion coefficient, relocation, and swelling are selected as the primary parameters for the present study.

Figure 1. Gaussian Processes (GP) performance analysis and Sensitivity Analysis (SA) results: a) GP surrogates vs. OFFBEAT predictions for the test values. b) Normalized residuals of the GP surrogate relative to the corresponding OFFBEAT test values (residuals scaled by the GPs predictive uncertainties), plotted together with the PDF of the standard Gaussian. c) SA measures: summary of the absolute means and standard deviations among the rods. The 95% confidence interval is shown for each input model parameter.

3.2. Surrogate modeling: Gaussian process surrogates application

The second component of the framework involves the use of surrogate modeling to ensure the computational feasibility of the MCMC algorithm. In this context, Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) is used as a surrogate modeling technique to emulate the output of OFFBEAT across the fuel rods. To construct the GP surrogates, the calibration parameters was varied using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS), ensuring a well-distributed set of points across the parameter space (defined as $\pm 50\%$ around their default values in OFFBEAT). A single dataset was generated and split into 80% of samples for training and 20% for testing. Also here, to enable efficient parallel execution, the Dakota software [10] was employed in combination with OFFBEAT.

Figure 1a compares the Gaussian Process (GP) surrogate predictions with the OFFBEAT computational

results for the testing dataset. Ideally, all points should lie on the bisector line, indicating perfect agreement between the two. In this case, the predictions fall within a $\pm 5\%$ error band, which can be considered satisfactory. The coefficients of determination (R^2) are also reported, all being around 0.99, confirming the good performance of the GP models.

The normalized residuals between the GP predictions and the OFFBEAT results are shown (see Figure 1b) in a single aggregated histogram that includes all rods. Ideally, these residuals should follow a standard normal (Gaussian) distribution. The observed distribution, however, shows some deviation due to the limited number of samples, with a few residuals noticeably distant from zero. This indicates the presence of certain test cases with relatively large prediction errors. These higher-error cases are primarily associated with input points located near the boundaries of the training data distribution—a well-known limitation of Gaussian Processes. To avoid introducing an additional and potentially significant source of uncertainty into the calibration process, the GP surrogates were employed not only for the calibration itself but also to generate the synthetic experimental data used as reference. This approach ensures internal consistency and reduces the risk of bias arising from boundary effects in the results.

Table II. Coefficient of determination (R^2) for the calibration rods.

Metric	ROD1	ROD10	ROD20	ROD31	ROD44	ROD58	ROD67	ROD99
R^2	0.994	0.990	0.985	0.995	0.993	0.992	0.992	0.993

3.3. Calibration: comparison between a standard calibration and a hierarchical approach

The third step of the framework involves performing the calibration and subsequently validating its results. This study compares the standard calibration approach, using the technique that has been shown to be limited for models with aleatoric uncertainty on the model parameters [5], with a hierarchical Bayesian calibration approach to evaluate their performance in fuel performance modeling. The hierarchical method employed here uses the MH-within-Gibbs algorithm as described in [4]. Both methods were initially run with 100,000 MCMC samples and a 50% burn-in to maintain consistent settings. For the hierarchical case involving the inference of five parameters, the number of samples was later increased by one order of magnitude to improve convergence stability. The figures, related to this case, presented here correspond to this final configuration. Calibration is first performed and results are presented for the inference of the most sensitive parameter, followed by the inference of the filtered sensitive parameters. The limitations of the proposed approach are highlighted, and potential avenues for future research are suggested.

3.3.1. Inference of the most sensitive parameter UO_2k

When calibrating only the most sensitive parameter, UO_2k , the hierarchical approach performs optimally. The posterior distribution closely matches the target distribution (Figure 2a), and the predictive quantiles, shown as ellipses indicating 95% credible intervals of the model predictions and 95% confidence intervals of the experiments, overlap the experimental measurements (Figure 2b), demonstrating statistical consistency. Convergence for this single-parameter case is fast and stable, with the chain thoroughly exploring the parameter space, as shown in Figure 3a. In contrast, the standard calibration strongly underestimates the parameter uncertainty and fails to capture the observed experimental variability.

3.3.2. Inference of the five main sensitive parameters

Extending the calibration to the five most influential parameters identified from the sensitivity analysis results in a total failure of the standard approach, while the hierarchical method shows only a slight degradation in performance (Figure 4). For this reason, the number of MCMC iterations for the hierar-

Figure 2. Calibration of UO_2k : (a) Posterior, prior and true distributions of UO_2k ; (b) Comparison of predictive quantiles against experimental measurements for validation rods. Ellipses show 95% credible intervals for model predictions (y-axis) and 95% confidence intervals for experimental measurements (x-axis). A zoom-in is shown for visualization.

Figure 3. UO_2k convergence plots for the hierarchical calibration. Shown are the evolution of the means, standard deviations, and experiment-specific parameters over the sampling iterations: (a) Calibration of only UO_2k . (b) Calibration of the five filtered parameters.

chical case was increased by one order of magnitude to achieve more stable convergence. For this case, as expected, the parameter with the most accurately inferred posterior distribution is the most sensitive one, UO_2k (Figure 4a), which governs most of the predictive behavior. The remaining parameters are considerably less impactful on the QoI, and thus the calibration process cannot properly recover their true values (Figure 4c). Instead, it identifies alternative combinations of parameters that produce comparable predictive outcomes (Figure 4c). The convergence plot for UO_2k (Figure 3b) reveal a trend in the Markov chains, indicating slower convergence and stronger interactions between parameters compared to the case involving the inference of only UO_2k (Figure 3a). Nevertheless, the prediction quantiles still encompass the experimental measurements. These results demonstrate that parameter sensitivity plays

Figure 4. Calibration of the five filtered parameters: (a) Posterior, prior and true distributions of UO_2k ; (b) Comparison of predictive quantiles against experimental measurements for validation rods. Ellipses show 95% credible intervals for model predictions (y-axis) and 95% confidence intervals for experimental measurements (x-axis). A zoom-in is shown for visualization; (c) Posterior, prior and true distributions of the other four filtered parameters.

a key role in the performance of hierarchical calibration, with the method being most robust for the most influential parameter. Future work will focus on addressing these issues by investigating ways to improve the performance of the Markov chain with additional samples or by incorporating further experiments.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of a hierarchical Bayesian calibration framework for fuel performance modeling under aleatoric model parameter uncertainty. By explicitly accounting for experiment variability, the hierarchical approach provides a more realistic quantification of predictive uncertainty compared to traditional calibration methods [5].

The results show that when calibrating the most sensitive parameter, UO_2k , the hierarchical method successfully recovers the target distribution and yields prediction intervals that encompass experimental measurements. Extending the calibration to the five most influential parameters identified through sensitivity analysis reveals the impact of parameter interactions: slower convergence. Nevertheless, the predictive quantiles, with 95% credible intervals for the model predictions and 95% confidence intervals for the experimental measurements, remain statistically consistent with the experimental data, highlighting the robustness of the method for the most sensitive parameters.

Overall, this work demonstrates that hierarchical calibration with Metropolis-Hasting within Gibbs algorithm is an effective approach for addressing aleatoric variability in nuclear fuel performance simulations. The method provides both accurate parameter inference and reliable uncertainty estimates,

offering a clear advantage over standard Bayesian calibration. Future work will focus on extending this framework to account for model bias and to incorporate the time dependency of the quantity of interest.

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